

Announcement on the Appointment of Professor Eric Maskin as Special Advisor to Humanitas Ark

Upon the approval of Mr. Hu Jiaqi, Chairman of Humanitas Ark, and following the deliberation and unanimous resolution of the Board, it is hereby officially announced that Professor Eric Maskin, the 2007 Nobel Laureate in Economics, has been appointed as Special Advisor to the organization. This appointment shall take effect from June 25, 2026, with a term of three years.

Professor Eric Maskin currently holds the position of Adams University Professor at Harvard University. He is one of the founding fathers of mechanism design theory, providing the foundational logic for market mechanism optimization and public policy design. For his groundbreaking work, which reshaped modern economics, he was awarded the Nobel Prize in Economics, offering vital theoretical support for the improvement of the modern economic system and sustainable global economic development. He is a highly influential and globally renowned economic scholar.

The appointment of Professor Maskin as Special Advisor represents an important step for the organization in pooling global top-tier wisdom, deepening international academic exchanges, and enhancing its professional capacity in the governance of technological risks. During his term of appointment, Professor Maskin will provide professional guidance for the organization's strategic planning; assist the organization in its global promotion and outreach; and help the organization establish connections with world-renowned scholars, scientists, and leaders.

We express our sincere gratitude to Professor Maskin for accepting this appointment, and we look forward to our close collaboration over the next three years. We firmly believe that Professor Maskin's profound academic expertise, broad international perspective, and deep insights into the patterns of global economic and social development will provide invaluable intellectual support for the organization's strategic planning and decision-making. We anticipate that with

Professor Maskin's assistance, Humanitas Ark will achieve new breakthroughs in its mission to ensure the perpetual survival and universal well-being of humanity.

Secretariat of Humanitas Ark

June 2026